

THE CONCEPT OF FAMILY IN ENGLISH LINGUISTIC CULTURE.

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<https://doi.org/10.5281/zenodo.13924645>

Annotation: This research paper explores the concept of family within the framework of English linguistic culture, tracing its origins from ancient Roman society to contemporary interpretations. It examines the etymological roots of the term "family," deriving from the Latin "familia," and discusses its evolution in meaning and significance across different historical periods. The paper highlights the transition from a broad collective understanding of family in ancient cultures to the modern emphasis on the nuclear family structure in English society, characterized by intimate relationships among a limited number of family members. Additionally, it addresses the impact of globalization, cultural exchanges, and mass media on the perception and values associated with family life. The study also delves into the dynamics of blended families, family functions, and the role of cultural influences on family structures, emphasizing the importance of family as a social institution for emotional and social development. Ultimately, the paper contemplates the future of family structures in response to evolving societal norms and the implications for familial relationships across generations.

Key words: family, blended, extended, hierarchy

The family as a social institution is peaceful and civilized. The friendly relationships in the union of husband and wife are an integral part of the mysterious formation of the family. The English word "family" is considered to come from the Roman word for hunger, the need for food. Acting together and pursuing its goals, the members of the Roman family formed a natural union, as people did once in their primitive unity, where different social, political, and functional interests are denied. So, for the ancient Romans, family was a kind of collective concept.

The concept of "family" has long held a significant place in East European cultures. It is perceived in the context of the values established by Slavic traditions and Orthodoxy. However, the increasing contacts with Western countries, English education, globalization, etc., lead to an active enrichment of the concept with English and European cultural components. It is clear that there is much that could be borrowed for Slavic linguoculturology, sociolinguistics, and linguodidactics, as well as from the history of the language.

The term "family" in English has been known since ancient times. In the Old English language, the concept possessed the form "fæmelle." The term is of Germanic origin and is related to "fiern" – "to lead" (the idea of an ancient community where family members gathered around the auditory to listen to the amusing old man's stories – "the Elders' Words," and the like). The term "Fiendlai," corresponding to "family" in Middle English, was first registered in a poem from 1595, and has the meaning of "relating to the family." Thus, they used the French term rather frequently.

Before conducting any linguistic analyses of family terms, it would be useful to review some aspects of the genealogical and anthropological method, one of the areas in which the problem being examined has long been the area of human culture in general. The English family is not a creation of modern society; it does not at all correspond to the Russian designation of this concept that has become firmly established in ethnography and everyday Russian life. It has its origins deeply rooted in prehistory on the not-so-broad little island that the Greeks named Albion. The investigation of these distant times has uncovered for us some strange but very distinct similarities with the events unfolding today. Barbarians of ancient Europe had settled themselves in the British Isles over 2000 years ago, where they built economic relations of a particular type that corresponded in many aspects to the feudal economy of the Middle Ages. At that time, the family began to acquire some of its characteristic forms, such as the obligatory passage of inheritance to the eldest son, the right of the father to make decisions about the marital lives of his children, or the submission of the remaining family members to his will. As a form of ownership, the family recognized only one kind of property, very particular in kind: weapons.

The concept "family" is quite broad, and its boundaries are dictated by different aspects, such as kinship, community, and consociation. The word "family" itself comes from the Latin "familia," the beginning of which is "famulus," meaning the estate man, i.e., the one who was economically most active in the household. The relationships inherent in the word "family," "kinship," "birth," "kin," etc., belong to the sphere of natural and national values, but unlike the terminology of the surrounding world, these relationships are individual and at the same time socially determined. This is because the birthplace, folk traditions, way of life, and cultural habits determine the social behavior of a person, their personality, and ethical norms. The resulting mutual influence of nature and certain conditions has a significant impact on the worldview, as a person perceives the world through a filter of their culture and

background, and this determines the method of solving tasks and the level of their concern.

The issue of the concept's delimitation is closely related to the definition of main terms. A "family" within the framework of English linguistic culture is traditionally considered as "a group consisting of one or two parents and their children." In the wording of a more general dictionary, "family" is represented as "a group of people who are related to each other, such as a mother, father, and their children." The etymological dictionary claims that the Latin "familia," from which this word derives, traditionally meant "slaves or the community of slaves and servants." These definitions apply to the mold of English linguistic culture, where the people's worldview links a "family" either with kindred ties or with the cohabitation of a group of people who usually share their everyday life in the same house. It is significant to emphasize that the community of housemates that form a "family" is governed by the fundamental features of the association's purpose.

The basic element of the domestic world of the English is a nuclear family consisting of parents, preferably both in their first marital union, and their young children. Thus, the idea of the ideal family for the English involves the minimum possible extension of the circle of living relatives. In the ideal model, all the necessary functions of the family are performed by the immediate members of the domestic group, who secure each other primarily through financial assistance, moral support, and intellectual interchange. The nuclear family model is a projection of social norms accepted in the past and became firmly established in the post-war period in the form of a separate set of valuation standards, which led to the broad dissemination in the popular psychology of a special psycho-economic family theory issued to account for the behavior of individual family members. The adherence of so many English adults to the principle of the nuclear family is, in this way, to a degree, an example of institutionalized inner opposition to hypothetical moral, economic, and social change. In the English linguistic culture, the scholars working on the concept of family emphasize its significance for the society in general. The Classical period philosophy viewed the family as the emotionally meaningful place where cultural transmission had taken place. The essay reveals the general meaning and structure of the concept FAMILY that has primacy in the European linguistic picture of the world. The struggle with the natural forces, the danger of death was the basis for uniting into the family which performed various functions, being the real common unit of life activity, reproduction and upbringing of

children, it protected its members, providing safe living space. The family was the natural community where mutual aid, care and love were valued.

The Old English word “family” was associated with financial welfare and the whole service staff until the beginning of the XVIII century. In the Modern Age, the interpreter of the word “family” in the linguistic picture of the world included the terms DIRECT FAMILY and EXTENDED FAMILY. The semantic model of the concept FAMILY distinguished the nuclear family concept from the cultural context. The extended family meaning focused on all the remote family members, being the subjects and objects of general family functions, person roles were constructed on the family love. The most significant person roles included children, mother, father, nephew and uncle. The concept FAMILY was included into the following cultural contexts: Native American kinship terminology, ancient Roman and Han Chinese households. In the linguistic picture of the world, the nuclear family was thoroughly analyzed. The term CONCEPT is characteristic of culture and is based on universal human cognitive strategies. In the linguistic picture of the world, it forms a peculiar system with the spatial, temporal, numerative, somatic, etc. concepts. In the world view aspect, the concept structure is revealed through the subjects with national character and contains integrated knowledge about the home country, its years, people, country sides that are available to the consciousness. The language game contributes to interpretation and fixation of the concept structure elements.

A blended family consists of a couple and their children from the present marriage, as well as the children from previous marriages. In some aspects, it can be looked at as an extended family. A typical blended family is a family where one or both partners in a couple who have children combine to form a new family. They tend to make different decisions about their living arrangements.

Since blended families are formed as a result of parental separation and re-partnering, step-relationships between family members predominate. They belong to different family structures and subcultures. A majority live in nuclear families. However, over a quarter live in single-parent families. There is no structural pattern to children's residence; half live in the couple's home, a quarter alternate residence, and another quarter are raised in a single-parent household without contact with the other parent or the other parent's family. In many families, children travel a long distance between homes. They may have relations with the other parent's family during school holidays and in the summer, and this usually involves travel. Where families live in close proximity,

children can be cared for and have contact with the other parent's family daily. If the children live far apart from the non-resident parent, they see them during the long summer holiday. Half have daily contact with their mother. Sisters have the highest mean frequency of contact with each other. They have equal time with one another and tend to be closer than sisters in the other non-residential family type. Family structure and patterns of parental contact are primary determinants for non-residential relationships.

Step-parents can have a significant role in the lives of their step-children who live with them. The most important factor is the age difference between the step-parent and the children. There is some evidence that, for stepparents and stepmothers, the nature of their relationship with the biological parent is important in terms of the involvement of child support variables. The ease with which the community can justify the care of stepdaughters is a measure. The frequency of visits from parents and the accommodation of step-parents and stepchildren determine the non-residential relationships. It can also measure the actual involvement of children and adjustment problems. If the stepchildren and stepmother have a good relationship, the children who live with them are likely to have the closest relationship with their non-residential parents and avoid adjustment problems. These results are consistent with adult standards, and research indicates that parents' satisfaction and children's well-being improve their performance. Studies also concluded that a general reciprocal parent-child relationship with parents is good for children, but an intense daily relationship with their spouse can result in child support difficulties.

Although a variety of factors may influence individual family dynamics, cultural factors within families can be understood in two broad conceptual categories. Family structure is the form a family takes in its makeup of people. Family function refers to the ways in which a family is organized to promote social and emotional growth, sharing, and the health and maintenance of its members. These two aspects of family, structure and function, have different cultural influences. Family functions can be filled by large groups of people who are not actual family. Often, as portrayed in literary stories, relatives become members of the family by aiding in the creation or function of the family or by sharing in the experiences of other members. Aspects of family processes, especially in the area of uniqueness and family purity, are strongly related to cultural values associated with individualistic or collectivist societies. Within collectivist cultures, individuals view themselves within the context of relationships with other family members and their roles within those

relationships. Maintaining solidarity among family members and fulfilling family obligations are paramount. The relative importance of family function can place family members in a paradox by sacrificing individual health and welfare for the preservation of the collective family system. To make matters even more complex, ties to family are also important to individuals from individualistic societies who may experience conflict between their ties to family and the desire for individual fulfillment.

Interest in language determining people's values and worldview has been increasing recently. At present, the language understandably appears as a profound source of cognition rather than a simple and transparent tool at the service of man. In connection with this understanding, language and linguistic units are observed not only at the level of formal semantic characteristics of individual code segments, but from the point of view of performed communicative-cultural functions, which primarily characterize the complete value of the language of personal communication. Seeing language in this light contributes to a better acquaintance of young people with not only a foreign language linguistic system structure, but also with values and attitudes in society. Therefore, communicating not only separate characteristics of linguistic units, but also values characteristic of English-speaking culture, we enrich the linguistic and cultural outlook of future teachers of English, helping to cultivate an understanding attitude towards the values of one's family and society as a whole, and its activity and work in preserving and nurturing these values.

One of the chief ways in which attitudes towards the family are perpetuated in society is through the mass media, through the exploitation of specific family-related language, verbal and non-verbal signs, such as gender codes and 'parenthood' stereotypes, intricately interwoven in most media representations of family life. Mass media, particularly advertising, are important social institutions, and they provide valuable insights into social structure and the relationship between ideologies and social structure. The institution of the family is rather accurately conceptualized and portrayed in various genres of mass media, which is why we have to be very cautious in dealing with media discourse, which both reflects this reality and has considerable impact on the audience, particularly on the so-called 'protected audience' (young children, in the majority of cases). Concerning advertising, family relations and connections are among the most frequent content of its utterances. Children play in various domestic settings or are related to some

family occasions much more frequently than adults, and these settings and occasions are seen as a preparation for their future family lives.

The most significant distortion, or rather, transformation in our view of the present model of English family life will affect the institution of marriage, which requires gradual adaptation to a changing society, the nature of social development, and the requirements of a new social policy. In the future, marriage will transform into the union of two individuals with general functions, no longer so rigid in type and structure. Greater emphasis will be given to kinship as a way of expressing family ties. In this respect, a legal and administrative structure will be created that clearly gives civil and social rights for any family groups living together, including members of different generations. Family life itself will undergo fundamental change. Adult children will combine full-time or short work and parental functions, thereby demonstrating the biological rhythm of family life. A high level of retirement benefits will release grandmothers from their full-time educational functions and will make it possible to have a family with independent income, as well as opportunities for voluntary professional or training activities. The skills and new roles of old age will also allow the older generation to participate in life in many other capacities, for example, by assuming family roles such as experts and co-presidents when considering particularly important family issues. This special influence of the parents' generation on the commonality of family relations will enable all the family to maintain not only relationships between different generations but also the maintenance of divergent interests of men, women, and children, as well as fathers, mothers, grandparents, and grandchildren. In general, the dynamics of the family are characterized by a rise in the hierarchy of family tensions, which is also necessary for the psychological life of each family member to be recognized. The family remains an important source of social heritage and the strongest socializing factor.

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